

Molecular and crystal structure of praziquantel. Spectroscopic properties and crystal polymorphism

Ana Borrego-Sánchez ^{a,b}, César Viseras ^b, Carola Aguzzi ^b, C. Ignacio Sainz-Díaz ^{a,*}

^a Instituto Andaluz de Ciencias de la Tierra (CSIC-University of Granada), Av. de las Palmeras 4, 18100 Armilla, Granada, Spain

^b Department of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Technology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Granada, Campus Cartuja s/n, 18071 Granada, Spain

article info

Keywords:

Praziquantel
DFT calculations
IR spectroscopy
Schistosomiasis
Molecular modeling

abstract

Schistosomiasis is a parasitic disease widely extended worldwide, mainly in the tropics and subtropics. Its pharmacological treatment is approached with praziquantel (PZQ), chemically named (*RS*)-2-(cyclohexylcarbonyl)-1,2,3,6,7,11b-hexahydro-4H-pyrazin-[2,1a]-isoquinolin-4-one. The PZQ commercial preparation is actually a racemic mixture, in which only the levo-enantiomer possesses anthelmintic activity. The knowledge of its spectroscopic and other chemical-physical properties is important to improve its applications. Therefore, the molecular and crystal structure of praziquantel have been investigated by means of calculations with classical mechanics and quantum mechanics methods based on Density Functional Theory (DFT), reproducing the experimental crystallographic and spectroscopic properties. Several crystal lattices of PZQ have been studied. Most of the intramolecular and intermolecular interactions of PZQ molecules in the crystal structure have been discussed. The vibration frequencies of the PZQ molecule were calculated with different molecular simulations and the assignments of some bands have been confirmed, such as, those of carbonyl groups.

1. Introduction

Praziquantel is the drug of choice for schistosomiasis. It is highly effective against all species of *Schistosoma* and against cestodes. It is usually administered in a single oral dose, which not only facilitates compliance but also has few side effects at short and long term. For its effectiveness, safety and cost-effectiveness features, the World Health Organization considers the praziquantel to be an essential drug (Passerini et al., 2006; WHO, 2015).

Schistosomiasis remains one of the most prevalent parasitic infections in the world caused by trematodes of the genus *Schistosoma*, which currently affects 250 million people worldwide out of a total of 783 million at risk (in 74 developing countries) (Trastullo et al., 2015) with about a half million deaths per year, mainly in the tropic and subtropical zones (Chitsulo et al., 2000; Rodrigues et al., 2010; Steinmann et al., 2006). There are two clinical forms of schistosomiasis, intestinal (caused by *Schistosoma mansoni* and *Schistosoma japonicum*) and urogenital (caused by *Schistosoma haematobium*). The adult worms of *S. mansoni* and *S. japonicum* reside in the mesenteric veins and *S. haematobium* in the host veins bladder plexus, place where fertilization occurs after male and female coupling, and subsequent eggs deposition. In particular, the *S. mansoni* extends almost all of Africa and South

America; *S. haematobium* in Africa and the Middle East and *S. japonicum* in China, the Philippines and some islands of Southeast Asia. Schistosomiasis is acquired by contact with fresh water contaminated with larvae of the parasite, called cercariae, released by different species of molluscs (intermediate hosts), which can penetrate into the individual skin (Hackey and Stirewalt, 1956). Pharmacology treatment mainly deals with the use of praziquantel for both intestinal and urinary way. Schistosomiasis prevention is problematic, since there is no vaccine, although its research is currently underway. The only possibility is chemotherapy treatment, for which there are three drugs, oxamniquine, albendazole and praziquantel. PZQ is active against all species of the parasite (Cioli et al., 1995), it has a high efficiency, low toxicity and is easy oral administration. This coupled with its versatility and low cost production makes it the chosen, as the drug of choice (Doenhoff et al., 2000). It is also effective against other parasitic infections, such as, flukes and tapeworms that infect pets. Hence it is considered an anthelmintic of broad spectrum. Its main disadvantage is its ineffectiveness against juvenile forms of the parasite (Cioli and Pica-Mattoccia, 2003). It is considered that the result of using a single drug for treating a widespread disease, might lead to such a dangerous situation as drug resistance.

Praziquantel was discovered at the beginning of the 1970s, when Bayer A.G. and E. Merck found that the group pyrazinoisoquinoline were effective anthelmintics (Groll, 1984; Andrews et al., 1983; Davis, 1982). In the PZQ molecule, chemically named (*RS*)-2-(cyclohexylcarbonyl)-1,2,3,6,7,11b-hexahydro-4H-

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ignacio.sainz@iact.ugr-csic.es (C.I. Sainz-Díaz).

pyrazin[2,1*a*]-isoquinolin-4-one (EP, 2011; USP, 2013), the oxo group in position 4 is essential for drug activity and that any modification of the skeleton ring suppresses activity. Furthermore, PZQ has a chiral center at the position 11b. The commercial preparation is actually a racemic mixture composed of equal parts "levo" isomer R (−), and "dextro" S (+), in which only the levo-enantiomer possesses molluscicide activity (Pax et al., 1978). Therefore, the PZQ anthelmintic activity is associated mainly with R(−)-enantiomer (Andrews, 1985).

The PZQ action mechanism is not exactly known, although most of the evidence points to an alteration of calcium homeostasis (Greenberg, 2005; Doenhoff et al., 2008). PZQ can act on various stages of development Schistosomas and can affect adult parasites, miracidia and cercariae, but has little or no effect on the eggs, sporocysts or schistosomula.

PZQ is hydrophobic and has low aqueous solubility. However, it is well absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract (Andrews, 1985). Oral doses are required to overcome high first pass liver metabolism and get appropriate target tissues concentrations (Leopold et al., 1978). With regard to their biopharmaceutical properties, PZQ is classified in Class II in Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) (Lindenberg et al., 2004; González-Esquivel et al., 2005). This means that it has very low water solubility and high permeability. Furthermore, PZQ shows drug resistance. At present there are numerous reports of *Schistosoma* strains with decreased drug sensibility. Due to its problematic, the PZQ continues being an object of study. However, surprisingly only a few works (Ahamed et al., 2012; Rodrigues et al., 2010) have been found related with the study of the molecular structure and intermolecular interactions in the crystal lattice, and spectroscopic properties of this drug. On the other hand, the racemate (RS)-PZQ crystallizes in an anhydrous crystal form that is different to that of the enantiomer (R) or (S)-PZQ, which are hemihydrates. Then, the racemate is a different crystal polymorph to the pure enantiomer PZQ. Previous works have tried to find new polymorphs of PZQ but always they obtained the same crystal forms (Toro et al., 2014). Therefore, one of the aims of this work is to find a computational methodology, which describes properly the molecular structure, and crystal lattices of PZQ and to identify normal vibration modes of the IR spectrum of PZQ.

2. Computational methodology

Calculations based on the Density Functional Theory (DFT) were performed by means of the DMOL3 program (Delley, 2000) using the generalized gradient approximation (GGA), and the revised Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof functional (RPBE) for the exchange–correlation potential (Hammer et al., 1999). Tridimensional periodical boundary conditions can be applied in this code, which uses molecular orbitals as a linear combination of atomic orbitals (LCAO), employing double zeta extended base functions including polarization functions (DNP) (Delley, 1990). Pseudopotentials with semi-core correction (DSPP) were used (Delley, 2002) in order to describe the interactions between electrons of the inner shells of atoms and valence electrons. The convergence threshold in the self-consistent cycle (SCF) of the energy calculation was 10^{-6} Ha. The calculation of frequency was based on the harmonic approximation using finite displacements of every atom. The harmonic vibrational frequencies were calculated by diagonalization of the Hessian matrix of the second derivative of the energy with respect to geometric changes generated by finite atomic displacements. This approach was previously used in other crystalline systems with good results (Escamilla-Roa and Sainz-Díaz, 2014).

On the other hand, since quantum mechanical methods described above may be difficult to explain the weak dispersion interactions in some cases, modeling using empirical interatomic potentials was also used for comparison. This approach is based on classical mechanics considering atoms as spheres with charges and interatomic potentials dependent of the distance between atoms. These potentials are characterized by a number of parameters that have been preset with

empirical observables constituting force fields. Several force fields (FF) were used, such as Compass (Sun, 1998), Universal (Rappe and Goddard, 1991) and the recently optimized CVFFH, based on the consistent valence force field (CVFF) (Heinz et al., 2006), that has provided good results in previous studies (Martos-Villa et al., 2013). To carry out these FF calculations, the Discover and Forcite programs were used within Materials Studio package (Accelrys, 2012). Different conditions were tested for calculating Van der Waals and Coulomb interactions. Atom based interactions with a cut-off of 18.5 Å was used for Universal and Compass FFs. With the CVFFH FF, the Ewald method with a cut-off of 15.5 Å yielded better convergence in the calculations according to previous works (Sainz-Díaz et al., 2011). Therefore, these conditions have been defined to undertake this work. On the other hand, the vibration frequencies were calculated following the same harmonic approximation used in the DFT calculations by means of finite displacements of every atom, where the energies are calculated with the FF.

In preliminary calculations various methods of atomic charges assignments were explored within the COMPASS FF: the Compass charges included in its own FF, and those calculated by the QEQ Method (charge equilibration) (Rappe and Goddard, 1991; Rick et al., 1995). The use of atomic charges of the own Compass FF yielded the closest values of lattice parameters to the experimental data. On the other hand, for CVFFH two water models were explored: SPC one (charges values of 0.41 and −0.82 for H and O atoms, respectively), and TIP4P model (charges of 0.417 and −0.834 for H and O atoms, respectively) (Rick et al., 1995; Berendsen et al., 1987). Net atomic charges associated to the electrostatic potential (ESP charges) (Besler et al., 1990) were calculated at quantum mechanical level using DMOL3 and they were applied to the COMPASS and CVFFH calculations.

The work was carried out using a modeling and simulation of materials software, Materials Studio 6.0 (Accelrys Inc., 2012) as well as graphical interface to calculate, analyze and study the crystal and molecular structures.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Praziquantel molecular structure

The crystal structure of (RS)-PZQ showed a certain disorder in the atomic positions, then the PZQ molecule was extracted from the experimental crystallographic data of the hemihydrate of (R)-PZQ crystal (Meyer et al., 2009) where no disorder was found in atomic positions. This molecule was fully optimized alone, in gas phase, with different theoretical methods (Fig. 1) comparing the calculated geometry with the only available experimental data that is in solid state (Table 1). Assuming that this calculated molecular structure is for an isolated molecule as in gas phase, the comparison with experimental values from a solid state can be considered valid for comparing the different calculation methods used in this work.

In general, the calculated C₁O bond distances are close to those from experimental data. In the hemihydrate crystal structure, the C₁O bond attached to the cyclohexyl group is much longer than those calculated. In this crystal structure, this carbonyl group interacts with a water molecule by hydrogen bonds enlarging the C₁O bond. In the OC\N bond, in both cases, $d(\text{OC}(\text{Cy})\backslash\text{N})$ and $d(\text{OC}\backslash\text{N})$, the calculated distances are larger than the experimental, being the closest those calculated with Compass. The same occurs with the bond H₂C\N of the CH₂ joined to the carbonyl and with the HC\N bond, the experimental values are close to those calculated with Compass. The OC\N and OC(Cy)\N bonds are shorter than the HC\N and H₂C(CO)\N bonds, due to the resonant delocalization of π electrons between N atom and carbonyl group.

Net atomic charges based on the Mulliken approximation and also atomic charges fitted to the electrostatic potential (ESP charges) were calculated (Besler et al., 1990) (see Tables S1 and S2 in Supplementary

Fig. 1. PZQ molecular structure optimized with COMPASS FF in two possible orientations. The atoms of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and oxygen are described in gray, white, blue and red, respectively.

Information). The O atoms of the carbonyl groups have the most negative charges of the molecule and most of the intermolecular interactions will be produced through these atoms, especially in crystal structures and its biological activity. However, some differences between Mulliken and ESP charges are observed. In general the ESP charges are higher than the Mulliken ones in H atoms according to previous works (Gross et al., 2002). The O atoms show similar Mulliken charges, whereas in the ESP charges the O atom of the heterocyclic part has a more negative charge than the other one. The N atoms show similar Mulliken charges, whereas the N atom joined to the carbonyl close to cyclohexyl ring shows a positive ESP charge and the other N atom shows a negative ESP charge. This difference is related with that in C8 that has a negative ESP charge whereas it has a low Mulliken charge. The positive ESP charge of N1 and the negative ESP charge in C8 indicate a participation of the electron lone pair of N1 into the N1-C8 bond assisted by the carbonyl O2 group.

Using atomic ESP charges from DMOL3 calculations within the COMPASS FF, the geometric features were slightly closer to experiment than those with the intrinsic charges of COMPASS FF. Therefore, these results conclude that the Compass FF combined with ESP atomic charges yields the closest values of the main geometric features, bond lengths and angles, of the PZQ molecule to the experimental one in solid state. Similar behavior with the ESP charges was found previously (Martos-Villa et al., 2013).

3.2. Conformational analysis.

In above results, some differences between calculated and experimental values in torsional angles are observed. These torsion angles can be also affected by the intermolecular interactions within the crystal structure. Molecular Dynamics simulations were performed for this isolated molecule at the NVT (298 K, steps of 1 fs for 5 ps) and NVE ensembles and no significant changes of the main dihedral angles by the rotation of bonds related with the *exo*-heterocyclic carbonyl group and cyclohexyl moiety was observed. Hence, a conformational analysis of these main dihedral angles should be explored. Then, the rotation of three dihedral angles has been studied independently with steps of

10° with the Compass FF. These angles control the spatial disposition of the cyclohexyl moiety with respect to the amido group and the relative disposition of the carbonyl group with respect to the heterocyclic part.

The rotation of the θ_1 [H₂C-C(H)-C=O] dihedral angle, which control de rotation of the cyclohexyl moiety with respect to the *exo*-heterocyclic carbonyl group, uses the C(H)-C(O) bond as a rotor and shows a conformer of minimal energy for $\theta_1 = 285^\circ$ within a zone of conformations between $\theta_1 = 170$ – 295° where the energy differences are less than 1.5 kcal/mol (Fig. 2a). This range is consistent with values found in experimental crystal structures, 261–270°, depending on the intermolecular structures described later. The global minimum conformer of Table 1 has a θ_1 value close to this range. A second conformer with an energy 2 kcal/mol higher than the minimum was localized at $\theta_1 = \pm 5^\circ$ that corresponds to the angle formed by the equivalent CH₂ group of the cyclohexyl moiety, where $\theta_1 = 14.3^\circ$ in the global minimum calculated above. In these conformers, the cyclohexyl ring is twisted with respect to the aromatic ring, and the planes of both rings form an angle of 45°–80° avoiding repulsion interactions of the H atoms with the H atoms of the heterocycle. The rotation of the θ_2 [H₂C(CO)-N-C=O] dihedral angle uses the C(O)-N bond as a rotor that describes the rotation of the *exo*-heterocyclic carbonyl group with respect to the heterocyclic ring with reference to the relative disposition with the heterocyclic carbonyl group. The analysis of this rotation shows a conformer of minimum energy for $\theta_2 = 195$ – 205° being close to the value of this dihedral angle in the global minimum of Table 1. This conformer maintains the minimal repulsion between the electron orbital of carbonyl O atom and the electron lone pair of the N atom and both carbonyl groups are oriented to opposite parts of the molecule naming as the conformer *anti*. Other conformers were obtained for $\theta_2 = 115$ – 130° and 325 – 355° . This last conformer, named *syn*, has both carbonyl groups oriented to the same part of the molecule. This conformer is present in the racemic (RS) crystal structure. The rotation of the θ_3 [H₂C(CH)-N-C(O)-CH(Cy)] dihedral angle is correlated with the previous one using the same C(O)-N bond as a rotor that describes the rotation of the C(O)-cyclohexyl moiety with respect to the CH₂ group joined to the chiral carbon. The analysis of this rotation

Table 1
Main geometrical features (bond lengths in Å and angles in °) of experimental and calculated molecular structure of PZQ. Cy = cyclohexyl.

Features	Exp. ^a	DC ^b	CVFFH ^c	FU ^d	DMOL3
$d(\text{CyC}=\text{O})$	1.229–1.226, 1.288 ^e	1.218 (1.221)	1.235	1.220	1.239
$d(\text{C}=\text{O})$	1.219–1.223	1.223 (1.221)	1.233	1.219	1.239
$d(\text{OC}-\text{N})$	1.342–1.350	1.355 (1.349)	1.365	1.383	1.378
$d[\text{OC}(\text{Cy})-\text{N}]$	1.342–1.360	1.357 (1.361)	1.377	1.387	1.396
$d[\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{CO})-\text{N}]$	1.450–1.455	1.474 (1.458)	1.505	1.479	1.462
$d(\text{HC}-\text{N})$	1.462–1.469	1.466 (1.459)	1.512	1.481	1.482
θ_1 [H ₂ C-C(H)-C=O]	28, 261–270	14, 255 (19, 260)	41, 275	14, 252	29, 266
θ_2 [H ₂ C(CO)-N-C=O]	181–189	205 (198)	176	184	177

^a Obtained from the experimental crystal structure of (RS)-PZQ (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013).

^b Calculated with Compass FF in Discover, the same values using the Forcite code with the same FF; values in brackets were calculated with quantum-mechanical ESP charges.

^c Calculated with CVFFH FF in Discover.

^d Calculated with Universal FF in Forcite.

^e From the experimental crystal structure of (R)-PZQ hemihydrate (Meyer et al., 2009).

Fig. 2. Energy profile (in kcal/mol) of the rotation of the θ_1 [H₂C- \dot{C} (H)- \dot{C} =O] (a), θ_2 [H₂C(CO)-N-C=O] (b), and θ_3 [H₂C(CH)-N-C(O)-CH(Cy)] (c) dihedral angles calculated with Compass FF.

shows two clear conformers with minimum energy are observed at $\theta_3 = 0-35^\circ$ and $175-195^\circ$, which correspond to the above *syn* and *anti* dispositions of the carbonyl groups and observed experimentally in the (*RS*)-PZQ and (*R*)-PZQ crystal structures, respectively. In both conformers, these C atoms, CH of cyclohexyl moiety and CH₂ joined to the chiral center, are coplanars maintaining the minimal repulsion between the H atoms of CH₂ groups.

3.3. Praziquantel crystalline structure

3.3.1. Enantiomer

PZQ is used mainly as a crystalline solid, hence a more realistic study is to calculate the PZQ in one of its crystal forms. Besides, the above former results of the calculated geometry of the isolated PZQ molecule only could be compared with experimental values of molecules within PZQ crystal structures. However, these molecules do not maintain the

same geometry in all crystal lattices and change depending on the intermolecular interactions in each crystal structure. The experimental information obtained after a search in Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) (Allen, 2002) shows several crystal forms. One of them corresponds to the anhydrous racemic mixture (TELCEU) (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013), another one to the isomer S hemihydrate (SIGBUG) (Liu et al., 2006), other to the isomer R hemihydrate (SIGBUG01) (Meyer et al., 2009) and the last one to the isomer R hemihydrate measured at low temperature (LIVFED) (Cedillo-Cruz et al., 2014). Additional income contains PZQ structural information of co-crystals and chemically replaced derivatives (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013).

The structure of the racemic crystal showed a certain disorder in atomic positions, see later. On the contrary, the atomic positions of the crystal structure of the hemihydrate of the enantiomer R of PZQ (SIGBUG01) are well defined. Then, this last structure was used for testing several computational methods. This crystal structure was

Fig. 3. a. A crystal structure of the hemihydrate of (*R*)-PZQ (SIGBUG01), views from the (010) and (001) planes. The atoms of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and oxygen are described by gray, white, blue and red color, respectively. b. Supercell $1 \times 2 \times 1$ of the hemihydrate of (*R*)-PZQ crystal sight in perspective from the plane (001) highlighting the intermolecular interactions with water molecule (right side).

measured at 298 K and other crystal structure of the same hemihydrate measured at 130 K was reported recently (Cedillo-Cruz et al., 2014). Both crystal structures are similar with slight differences in the cell parameters and different orientation and atomic positions. Both crystal lattices are in C2 space group and models with the unit cell in the P1 symmetry were generated for both. This unit cell has 194 atoms, 4 praziquantel molecules and 2 water molecules (Fig. 3).

All atomic positions were optimized with different methods considering a constant volume and later the crystal lattice was also optimized along with all atom positions at variable volume. The crystal lattice parameters of the optimized structures were compared with experimental data (Table 2). The Compass and CVFFH FFs with Discover yielded crystal lattice parameters close to experimental data. Both are closer to the data obtained at 130 K that were slightly smaller than that obtained at 298 K, as it was expected since the calculations were made at 0 K. The Universal FF did not yield good results. The optimization at variable cell in Forcite with Compass FF yielded worse results than in Discover. Hence the best computational method was Discover with both FFs, Compass and CVFFH.

The optimization of the crystal structure obtained at 298 K (SIGBUG01) (Meyer et al., 2009) yielded the same lattice cell as that obtained at 130 K (LIVFED) (Cedillo-Cruz et al., 2014).

The same relative disposition of PZQ molecules was observed in experimental and calculated crystal lattice structures. The PZQ molecules are packing in a tail-head facing orientation, where the cyclohexyl ring is facing to the aromatic ring of the vicinal molecule with electrostatic interactions between some H atoms of cyclohexyl and the π electron cloud of the aromatic ring. On the other side of the molecule, one water molecule joins two PZQ molecules by means of the carbonyl groups with bridging H bonds (Fig. 3). The main geometrical features of the molecules in the calculated crystal show (Table 3) the same differences observed above in the isolated PZQ molecule (Table 1). No significant differences were observed between the different models of water, due to the low proportion of water in these crystals. The use of Compass FF within Discover yielded the closest geometry to the experimental data, though the values calculated with the DMOL3 method showed also a good agreement with experiment. The bonds H2C(CO)-N, OC-N and HC-N are lightly longer than the experimental. The experimental $d(\text{OH})$ bond length did not fit with the calculated ones, because the experimental values come from an estimated placement of H atoms during the refinement of the crystal structure from the electron density obtained by X-ray diffraction and this bond can be overestimated in one from Meyer et al. (2009) and underestimated in the other from Cedillo-Cruz et al. (2014). No significant differences in the bond lengths and angles of PZQ molecules in the crystal structure were observed between the structures optimized at fixed or at variable volume, except in the intermolecular interactions (Tables 3 and 4). The cyclohexyl ring is twisted 45° with respect to the aromatic ring according with experimental structure where the twisting angle is 70° . In the

Table 2
Values of crystal lattice parameters of the hemihydrate of (R)-PZQ, fully optimized with variable volume with different theoretical methods and compared with the experimental lattice (distances in Å and angles in $^\circ$).

Lattice parameters	Exp	DCCVa	VHCV ^b	VHsCV ^c	FCCV ^d	FUCV ^e
<i>a</i>	27.05 ^f , 26.30 ^g	26.63	26.30	26.24	27.52	28.09
<i>b</i>	6.02 ^f , 6.01 ^g	6.17	6.21	6.19	6.04	6.04
<i>c</i>	11.36 ^f , 11.14 ^g	10.98	10.98	11.02	10.86	10.77
β	112.5 ^f , 111.1 ^g	110.3	109.2	109.2	114.4	114.0

^a Calculated with the Compass FF in Discover.

^b Calculated with CVFFH with their own charges for water atoms in Discover.

^c Calculated with CVFFH with the SPC water model Discover. The same result was obtained with the TIP4P water model in same conditions.

^d Calculated with Compass FF in the Forcite code.

^e With the Universal FF in the Forcite code.

^f Experimental crystal structure at 298 K (Meyer et al., 2009).

^g Experimental data at 130 K (Cedillo-Cruz et al., 2014).

heterocycle joined to the aromatic ring, the CH₂ group joined to N atom is shifted upwards from the aromatic plane. This makes that the other heterocycle is shifted downwards with respect to the aromatic plane. In all PZQ molecules of these hemihydrate crystal structures, the carbonyl groups are oriented in opposite directions.

It is remarkable the large difference in the bond length of the carbonyl group joined to the cyclohexyl moiety. This could be explained by the H bond interaction with the water molecule. However this interaction exists also in the crystal studied at 130 K and the bond length is significantly shorter and closer to our calculations. Hence, the crystal structure analyzed at 298 K overestimated the C=O bond length.

The crystal structure of the hemihydrate of the enantiomer S of PZQ obtained experimentally at 293 K (Liu et al., 2006) is similar to that of the isomer R studied at 298 K, with the same cell parameters and space group. However, the atomic positions were different owing to the different orientation with respect to the origin of the coordinates system used for the refinement. Nevertheless, a model of one unit cell of this crystal of (S)-PZQ was generated and optimized with DISCOVER and COMPASS FF obtaining the same cell parameters that those of the (R)-PZQ crystal (Fig. 4). However, small differences are observed in some bond lengths and angles (Table 5). In this crystal, the experimental bond length of the carbonyl group joined to the cyclohexyl moiety is closer to that of the R isomer measured at 130 K and to our calculated values. This corroborates that the bond length of the crystal determined by Meyer et al. (2009) overestimated the C=O bond length.

3.3.2. Racemate (RS)-PZQ

A different crystal structure was reported for the racemate (RS)-PZQ. This is an anhydrous crystal with no water molecule in the crystal lattice and a P-1 space group (293 K) in a triclinic system (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013). This crystal is a racemate crystal where the enantiomers are mixed forming the crystal lattice. This is not an aggregate or solid solution of crystals of separated enantiomers with crystals of R and crystals of S forms. However, the refinement quality is lower (8% of residual indetermination) than in the enantiomer crystals (4%). This is owing to disordering in atomic positions. The unit cell is formed by 8 PZQ molecules, where the atomic positions of four of them are well determined, whereas the other four molecules have well localized the cyclohexyl atoms but the heterocyclic and aromatic atoms are disordered. This crystal structure file includes all possible atomic positions as an average view. These atoms can adopt slightly different positions in vicinal cells and supercells will be necessary to represent all atomic positions. Then in the description of the electron density of a unit cell some duplicate positions are obtained, indicating that there is some likelihood that these atoms occupy those positions of considering various neighboring cell-statistical unit (Fig. 5a). From this experimental lattice a model of one unit cell of this racemate was created deleting all atom duplications maintaining similar bond lengths and angles to the other ordered molecules and a more ordered system was obtained (Fig. 5b).

Our calculations reproduce the experimental crystal structure of (RS)-PZQ with a deviation less than 1% in lengths and less than 4% in angles of cell parameters (Table 6). No strong intermolecular H bonds like in the hemihydrate was detected, this facilitates the partial disorder observed. The carbonyl groups are oriented towards the heterocyclic H atoms owing to electrostatic interactions, and the aromatic rings are parallel to the heterocyclic rings of vicinal molecules establishing a possible π - π interaction between these rings. The enantiomer molecules are associated each other in racemic pairs of PZQ. The cyclohexyl ring is twisted with respect to the vicinal carbonyl group. This consistent with the above conformational analysis, where the conformation of minimum energy had the dihedral angle $\theta_1 = 280^\circ$. The cyclohexyl plane forms a twist angle of 80° with respect to the aromatic plane. On the contrary of the above hemihydrate crystals, in RS crystals the carbonyl groups are oriented in the same direction, adopting the above named conformer *syn*, that corresponds to the second conformer

Table 3
Main geometrical features (Å) of the crystal structure of hemihydrate of (*R*)-PZQ optimized at fixed volume with different computational methods and experimental data.

Features	Exp	DCCF ^a	VHCF ^b	VHsCF ^c	FCCF ^d	FUCF ^e	DMOL3
d(CyC=O)	1.288 ^f , 1.233 ^g	1.220	1.235	1.236	1.227	1.224	1.251
d(C=O)	1.220 ^f , 1.227 ^g	1.226	1.230	1.231	1.205	1.207	1.245
d(OC-N)	1.351 ^f , 1.346 ^g	1.355	1.362	1.364	1.366	1.367	1.364
d(OC(Cy)-N)	1.350 ^f , 1.357 ^g	1.350	1.371	1.369	1.365	1.379	1.370
d(H ₂ C(CO)-N)	1.455 ^f , 1.453 ^g	1.470	1.497	1.499	1.456	1.481	1.465
d(HC-N)	1.462 ^f , 1.469 ^g	1.472	1.513	1.516	1.476	1.476	1.480
d(OH...OC)	1.715 ^f , 1.836 ^g	1.704	2.605	1.688 (1.737)	1.917	2.185	1.817
d(HO...OC)	2.749 ^f , 2.653 ^g	2.662	3.312	2.698 (2.703)	2.872	3.011	2.796
d(O-H)	1.065 ^f , 0.850 ^g	0.968	0.958	1.012 (0.968)	0.979	0.984	0.980
θ ₁ (H ₂ C-C(H)-C=O)	28, 261–266	18.8, 259.2	32, 265.6	30, 263.7 (30, 263.6)	13.9, 253.9	14.7, 252	27.7, 265
θ ₂ (H ₂ C(CO)-N-C=O)	181–187	195	169.8	174.8 (174.8)	213	200.7	182.3

^a Calculated with Discover and Compass FF with fixed volume.

^b Calculated with Discover and CVFFH at fixed volume.

^c Calculated with Discover and CVFFH with SPC water model at fixed volume. The same result was obtained with the TIP4P water model in the same conditions, except in the values described in brackets.

^d Calculated with Forcite and Compass FF at fixed volume.

^e Calculated with Forcite and Universal FF at fixed volume.

^f Experimental crystal structure at 298 K (Meyer et al., 2009).

^g Experimental data at 130 K (Cedillo-Cruz et al., 2014).

observed in the above conformational analysis with the rotation of the θ₂ and θ₃ dihedral angles. This new conformer was extracted from the crystal structure as an isolated molecule and was optimized with COMPASS and the same conformation was maintained being only 0.525 kcal/mol less stable than the global minimum obtained above for PZQ molecule. On the other hand the global dipolar moment was calculated for both conformers. The conformer *syn* is much more polar (μ = 6.3 D) than the conformer *anti* (μ = 1.5 D). This can indicate that the conformer *syn* will be more stable in polar media and this high μ can justify the stability of the crystal packing of the (*RS*)-crystal where no water and no H bonding were necessary. The intermolecular interactions in this racemic crystal are mainly electrostatic ones between dipoles. The vicinal molecules are oriented in opposite sense where the dipole moments are opposite establishing attractive dipole-dipole electrostatic interactions.

The CyC=O, H₂C(CO)-N and C=O bond lengths of the calculated structure are shorter than the experimental and the OC(Cy)-N, OC-N and HC-N bond lengths are longer than the experimental ones (Table 7).

Table 4
Main geometrical features (Å) of the crystal structure of the hemihydrate of (*R*)-PZQ optimized at variable volume with different computational methods.

Features	DCCV ^a	VHCV ^b	VHsCV ^c	FCCV ^d	FUCV ^e
d(CyC=O)	1.220	1.235	1.236	1.224	1.212
d(C=O)	1.226	1.231	1.231	1.218	1.205
d(OC-N)	1.356	1.364	1.365	1.350	1.372
d(OC(Cy)-N)	1.350	1.373	1.370	1.358	1.370
d(H ₂ C(CO)-N)	1.471	1.499	1.499	1.441	1.446
d(HC-N)	1.472	1.514	1.515	1.463	1.464
d(OH...OC)	1.708	2.597	1.679 (1.728)	1.816	2.232
d(HO...OC)	2.657	3.077	2.687 (2.693)	2.782	2.811
d(O-H)	0.967	0.957	1.012 (0.968)	0.989	1.001
θ ₁ (H ₂ C-C(H)-C=O)	16.6,	30.9,	29, 262.1 (29,	20.1,	15.3,
	258.1	264.1	262.1)	262.8	253.8
θ ₂ (H ₂ C(CO)-N-C=O)	196	172.9	175.6 (175.6)	192.5	188.2

^a Calculated with Compass in Discover.

^b Calculated with CVFFH in Discover.

^c Calculated with Discover and CVFFH with SPC water model. The same result was obtained with the TIP4P water model in the same conditions, except in the values described in brackets.

^d Calculated with Forcite and Compass.

^e Calculated with Forcite and Universal FF.

3.3.3. Cohesive energy.

Cohesive energy has been calculated with COMPASS FF in DISCOVER for the hemihydrate of one enantiomer and the racemate crystals. The cohesive energy can be defined as the difference between the energy of each molecule isolated and the energy of the crystal:

$$\Delta E_{RS} = E_{RS} - 8E_{PZQ \text{ MOL}}$$

$$\Delta E_R = E_R - 4E_{PZQ \text{ MOL}} - 2E_{\text{water}}$$

In all cases the cohesive energy is negative, showing that the formation of the crystal is exothermic and thermodynamically favourable. This energy is stronger with the crystals optimized at variable volume than in the crystals optimized at constant volume. The racemic RS crystal is 105.6 kcal/mol per unit cell more stable than the hemihydrate enantiomeric crystal owing to the higher number of PZQ molecules per unit cell in the RS crystal. However, the (*R*)-PZQ crystal has a stronger cohesive energy per PZQ molecule (−48.1 kcal/mol per PZQ molecule) than the RS crystal (−37.2 kcal/mol per PZQ molecule) due to the presence of water molecules in the hemihydrate.

3.4. Infrared spectroscopy

In previous reports on PZQ, the IR spectra were used only as identification tool rather than as a way for a further structural knowledge (Schepers et al., 1987; Liu et al., 2004; Passerini et al., 2006; Mainardes et al., 2006; Rodrigues et al., 2010; Chaud et al., 2013). However, some differences and discrepancies were found in the assignments of the vibration bands in previous works, especially in the carbonyl groups modes. Infrared spectroscopy shows bands corresponding to vibration absorption between atoms and therefore is also closely related to atomistic studies. In the above calculations, molecular structures were optimized. In the minimum energy structure the atom positions can be altered slightly along the directions of the Cartesian axes of the three-dimensional structure in both senses, making 6N finite atomic displacements, where N is the number of atoms. These changes produce an alteration of energy and thus the derivative of energy with respect to such geometrical change, that is what is called the atomic forces, can be calculated and the process, named Forces Analysis, enable us to calculate the frequencies of the normal modes of atomic vibrations. This allows us to compare these frequencies with those observed experimentally as infrared spectrum bands. Besides these theoretical calculations it facilitates the allocation of certain bands observed in

Fig. 4. Crystal structure of (RS)-PZQ, (a) from experimental (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013) data, and an ordered model (b).

the spectrum and not defined previously in previous experimental studies or to clarify discrepancies in its allocation among previous authors.

Therefore, in this study the frequencies of the vibration normal modes of the PZQ molecule were calculated with the procedure described above using COMPASS FF and DMOL3 for energy calculations of each step and compared with literature data (Table 8). PZQ shows experimentally two main characteristic bands in the range 3028–2852 cm^{-1} assigned to stretching vibration $\nu(\text{CH})$ of CH and CH_2 groups, however, no specific assignments was reported for the different CH groups of the PZQ molecule (Schepers et al., 1987; Passerini et al., 2006; Mainardes et al., 2006; Rodrigues et al., 2010; Chaud et al., 2013). In this range the calculated frequencies are consistent with experimental values and the relative frequency differences are similar in both calculations methods, being slightly higher those of DMOL3 for frequencies higher than 3000 cm^{-1} . No significant differences are observed between frequencies calculated by compass FF with and without ESP atomic charges calculated at quantum mechanical level, except in the modes of the polar groups, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, or modes of bonds close to the polar groups, COCH_2N . In our calculations several types of CH bonds can be distinguished. Aromatic CH bonds show $\nu(\text{CH})$ at higher frequencies than the aliphatic ones, being in the middle those CH_2 groups of the heterocyclic moiety. In these last groups, COCH_2N , CH_2N in β position with respect to the aromatic ring and CH_2N group in the heterocyclic ring, the frequency of the $\nu(\text{CH})$ mode depends on the relative orientation of the C-H bond with respect to the neighbor C=O bond. The C-H bond that vibrates in a parallel direction with respect

to the vicinal C=O bond, has a higher frequency than the other C-H bond with different orientation. This is due to the electrostatic effect of the C=O dipole on the C-H stretching vibration that is stronger with the C-H bond that is in a parallel disposition with C=O, requiring this stretching more energy and then higher frequency.

The experimental $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ bands are observed in the 1736–1627 cm^{-1} range (Chaud et al., 2013; Mainardes et al., 2006; Passerini et al., 2006; Rodrigues et al., 2010; Schepers et al., 1987). In some spectra, a splitting or complex structure was observed but neither discussion

Table 5

Main bond lengths (Å) and angles ($^\circ$) values of the crystal structure of the hemihydrate of (S)-PZQ (SIGBUG), experimental data and optimized with Discover/Compass at fixed (CF) and variable (CV) volume.

Features	Experimental ^a	DCCF ^b	DCCV ^c
d(CyC=O)	1.232	1.220	1.220
d(C=O)	1.223	1.226	1.226
d(OC-N)	1.351	1.355	1.356
d(OC(Cy)-N)	1.346	1.350	1.350
d(H ₂ C(CO)-N)	1.451	1.470	1.471
d(HC-N)	1.463	1.472	1.472
d(OH...OC)	2.033	1.702	1.706
d(HO...OC)	2.751	2.661	2.657
d(O-H)	0.724	0.968	0.967
θ_1 (H ₂ C-C(H)-C=O)	27.5, 265.4	18.8, 259.2	16.6, 257.3
θ_2 (H ₂ C(CO)-N-C=O)	178	165	164.3

^a Obtained from experimental crystal structure (Liu et al., 2006).

^b Calculated at fixed volume.

^c Calculated at variable volume.

Fig. 5. Simulated IR spectra (frequency in cm^{-1}) of the *anti* (a) and *syn* (b) conformers of the calculated PZQ molecule.

Table 6

Lattice parameters (distances in Å and angles in degrees) of the (RS)-PZQ crystal structure, experimental (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013) values and fully optimized structure at variable volume with Discover Compass FF.

Lattice parameters	Experimental	DCCV
<i>a</i>	10.45	10.35
<i>b</i>	15.11	15.02
<i>c</i>	22.96	23.23
α	99.5	95.6
β	98.4	96.7
γ	108.3	111.3

about it nor assignment was reported. Some differences in experimental studies are observed: Schepers et al. (1987) reported a broad band (1680–1625 cm⁻¹) centered at 1650 cm⁻¹; similar band was reported at 1630 cm⁻¹ by Mainardes et al. (2006) and at 1736 cm⁻¹ by Rodrigues et al. (2010); Chaud et al. (2013) showed a complex band centered at 1651 cm⁻¹; and Passerini et al. (2006) reported two bands at 1649 and 1627 cm⁻¹. The calculated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ frequencies are slightly higher than experimental ones; nevertheless this splitting is also detected in our calculations. The frequency difference is small 16 and 12–34 cm⁻¹ in COMPASS and DMOL3, respectively. However, the assignments of the bands are different in each calculation method. In COMPASS, the higher frequency band is assigned to the carbonyl group joined to the cyclohexyl moiety, whereas in DMOL3 this band is assigned to the other carbonyl group. This discrepancy is due to the similar local environment for both C=O bonds and it can justify the lack of relative assignment reported experimentally, where this splitting could change in solid state or in dissolution. However, the COMPASS calculations applying atomic ESP charges yielded the same assignment that in DMOL3 (Table 8). Further studies related with this item should be performed.

Around 1450–1200 cm⁻¹ bands of C-H bonds deformation vibration or bending $\delta(\text{CH})$ and bands of stretching vibration of the C-N bonds $\nu(\text{CN})$ were reported experimentally (Mainardes et al., 2006; Rodrigues et al., 2010) (Table 8). The calculated frequencies of $\delta(\text{CH})$ mode are higher than the experimental values for all calculation levels. The aromatic H atoms show higher $\delta(\text{CH})$ frequencies than the aliphatic ones. The $\gamma(\text{CH})$ modes and other that appear at lower frequencies is difficult to assign due to the coupling with other atomic vibrations of the whole molecule.

Spectra of the calculated (DFT) *anti* and *syn* conformers of the PZQ molecule were simulated, observing that the most intense bands are those of $\nu(\text{CO})$ according with experiment (Fig. 5). The $\nu(\text{CH})$ frequencies are similar for both conformers, except in the COCH₂N group, where they are higher in *syn* than in *anti*, due to the effect of the carbonyl groups. In the *syn* conformers both carbonyls groups are oriented to these COCH₂N group and the effect of these local dipoles is higher

Table 7

Main bond lengths and angles (distances in Å and angles in degrees) of the crystal structure of (RS)-PZQ, experimental values and calculated values of the structures optimized at fixed and variable volume with Discover Compass FF.

Features	Experimental ^a	DCCF ^b	DCCV ^c
d(CyC=O)	1.226–1.229	1.219	1.216–1.219
d(C=O)	1.219–1.223	1.224	1.223–1.226
d(OC-N)	1.342–1.350	1.355	1.358–1.361
d(OC(Cy)-N)	1.342–1.360	1.351–1.364	1.356–1.369
d(H ₂ C(CO)-N)	1.453	1.457–1.467	1.459–1.467
d(HC-N)	1.461	1.465–1.480	1.470
		15.7–31.6,	23.2–32.2,
θ_1 (H ₂ C-C(H)-C=O)	31.5, 270	25.6–271.9	25.2–273.1
θ_2 (H ₂ C(CO)-N-C=O)	2.3	2.7–14.5	1.6–7.7

^a Obtained from experimental crystal structure (Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013).

^b Calculated with Discover Compass at fixed volume.

^c Calculated with Discover Compass at variable volume.

Table 8

Calculated and experimental frequencies (cm⁻¹) of the main modes of vibration of the PZQ molecule.

Mode	Compass ^a	DMOL3 <i>anti</i> (<i>syn</i>) ^b	Exp. ^c
$\nu(\text{CH})^d$	3074–3046 (3072–3043)	3183–3126 (3156–3128)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)_{\text{COCH}_2\text{N}}$	3016 (3036, 2966)	3102 ^e , 2950 ^f (3108, 3003)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)^{e,g}$	2981 (2983)	3152 (3133)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)^{e,h}$	2971 (2955)	3107 (3108)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)^i$	2967, 2919 (2964, 2916)	3046, 3001 (3051, 3001)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)^{f,g}$	2909 (2918)	3004 (2968)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)^{f,h}$	2898 (2891)	3013 (2993)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH}_2)^j$	2955–2949 _{as} , 2911–2902 _s (2957–2945 _{as} , 2909–2900 _s)	3050–2967 (3077–2971)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH})^l$	2940 (2942)	3002, 2987 (3005)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CH})^k$	2906 (2903)	2920 (2934)	3028–2852
$\nu(\text{CO})$	1703 (1718)	1662 (1673)	1736 ^m , 1651–1627
$\nu(\text{CO})^n$	1719 (1702)	1650 (1639)	1736 ^m , 1651–1627
$\delta(\text{CH})^d$	1662–1615, 1513 (1660–1615)	1593–1487 (1589–1482)	1450–1200
$\delta(\text{CH})^l$	1481–1467 (1483–1468)	1489–1467 (1490–1437)	1450–1200
$\delta(\text{CH})^g$	1599, 1456 (1594, 1462)	1466 (1467)	1450–1200
$\delta(\text{CH})^h$	1548, 1433 (1541, 1417)	1462 (1461)	1450–1200
$\delta(\text{CH})_{\text{COCH}_2\text{N}}$	1502 (1514–1508)	1435 (1450)	1450–1200
$\delta(\text{CH})^i$	1464	1437 (1443)	1450–1200
$\gamma(\text{CH})^j$	(1427, 1414)		1450–1200
$\gamma(\text{CH})^{g,h}$		1404 ^h , 1360 ^g	1450–1200
$\gamma(\text{CH})_{\text{COCH}_2\text{N}}$	1314, 1278 (1343, 1313)	1309 (1218)	1450–1200

^a Values calculated with ESP atomic charges are in brackets.

^b Conformer *syn* values are in brackets.

^c Schepers et al. (1987), Passerini et al. (2006), Mainardes et al. (2006), Chaud et al. (2013), Rodrigues et al. (2010).

^d CH bonds of the aromatic ring, in some $\delta(\text{CH})$ modes coupling with $\nu(\text{C}_\text{C})$ were observed.

^e With the vibration mode parallel to the carbonyl bond.

^f CH oriented perpendicularly to the carbonyl bond.

^g Stretching of the C\text{N}H bond of the CH₂ group in the heterocyclic ring (CH\text{N}CH₂\text{N}).

^h CH₂ group in β position with respect to the aromatic ring.

ⁱ CH₂ group in α position with respect to the aromatic ring.

^j Cyclohexyl group.

^k Stretching of the CH of the chiral carbon.

^m From Rodrigues et al. (2010).

ⁿ Symmetric stretching of the CO joined to the cyclohexyl group.

than in *anti*. On the contrary the $\nu(\text{CH})$ frequencies of the NCH₂ group of heterocyclic ring of *syn* (3133 and 2968 cm⁻¹) are lower than in *anti* (3152 and 3004 cm⁻¹), due to the lack of the effect of carbonyl group. On the other hand, the frequency difference in $\nu(\text{CO})$ between both carbonyl groups is higher in *syn* than in *anti* (Table 8, Fig. 5).

4. Conclusions

Our atomistic computational methods have reproduced the molecular and all crystal structures of PZQ in both enantiomers and racemic form. The Compass FF and DMOL3 methods yielded the closest results to experimental values. Compass described well the geometry and DMOL3 calculated well the infrared frequencies. In gas phase, as isolated molecules the conformer *anti* is more stable than the *syn* one. However, this last one is much more polar than the *anti* one. This means that in polar media the most stable conformer will be probably the conformer *syn*. Hence, in an aqueous physiological medium the conformer *syn* will interact with the receptor. Probably the orientation of both carbonyl groups to the same side can facilitate the coordination with Ca²⁺

cations or H bonding interactions with aminoacids of the receptor active site.

The intermolecular interactions of the hemihydrate crystals are different that those of the racemic crystal. The carbonyl groups and the aromatic ring are responsible of the molecular packing in the crystal forms. The local environments of these carbonyl groups are different in each crystal structures adopting different conformations that can affect to the vibration frequencies. Further studies of the solid state of this drug are necessary to understand more deeply its properties.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2016.04.023>.

Acknowledgements

Authors are thankful to the Regional Andalusian Projects (RNM363 and RNM1897) and the Spanish MINECO Projects (FIS2013-48444-C2-2-P) for financial support and to the Supercomputational Center of Universidad de Granada for computing facilities.

References

- Accelrys Materials Studio, version v 6.0. Accelrys Inc., San Diego, USA.
- Ahamed, M., Chan, B., Jensen, P., Todd, M.H., 2012. The outcome of the oxidations of unusual enediamide motifs is governed by the stabilities of the intermediate iminium ions. *PLoS One* 7, 47224.
- Allen, F.H., 2002. The Cambridge Structural Database: a quarter of a million crystal structures and rising. *Acta Crystallogr. B* 58, 380–388.
- Andrews, P., 1985. Praziquantel: mechanisms of anti-schistosomal activity. *Pharmacol. Ther.* 29, 129–156.
- Andrews, P., Thomas, H., Pohlke, R., Seubert, J., 1983. Praziquantel. *Med. Res. Rev.* 3, 147–200.
- Berendsen, H.J.C., Grigera, J.R., Straatsma, T.P., 1987. The missing term in effective pair potentials. *J. Phys. Chem.* 91, 6269–6271.
- Besler, B.H., Merz Jr., K.M., Kollman, P.A., 1990. Atomic charges derived from semiempirical methods. *J. Comput. Chem.* 11, 431–439.
- Cedillo-Cruz, A., Aguilar, M.I., Flores-Alamo, M., Palomares-Alonso, F., Jung-Cook, H., 2014. A straightforward and efficient synthesis of praziquantel enantiomers and their 4'-hydroxy derivatives. *Tetrahedron* 25, 133–140.
- Chaud, M.V., Lima, A.C., Vila, M.M.D.C., Paganelli, M.O., Paula, F.C., Pedreiro, L.N., Gremião, M.P.D., 2013. Development and evaluation of praziquantel solid dispersions in sodium starch glycolate. *Trop. J. Pharm. Res.* 12, 163–168.
- Chitsulo, L., Engels, D., Montresor, A., Savioli, L., 2000. The global status of schistosomiasis and its control. *Acta Trop.* 7, 41–51.
- Cioli, D., Pica-Mattoccia, L., 2003. Praziquantel. *Parasitol. Res.* 90, 3–9.
- Cioli, D., Pica-Mattoccia, L., Archer, S., 1995. Antischistosomal drugs: past, present...and future? *Pharmacol. Ther.* 68, 35–85.
- Davis, A., 1982. Available chemotherapeutic tools for the control of schistosomiasis. *Behring Inst. Mitt.* 71, 90–103.
- Delley, B., 1990. An all-electron numerical method for solving the local density functional for polyatomic molecules. *J. Chem. Phys.* 92, 508–517.
- Delley, B., 2000. From molecules to solids with the DMol3 approach. *J. Chem. Phys.* 113, 7756–7764.
- Delley, B., 2002. Hardness conserving semilocal pseudopotentials. *Phys. Rev. B* 66, 1551251–1551259.
- Doenhoff, M.J., Kimani, G., Cioli, D., 2000. Praziquantel and the control of schistosomiasis. *Parasitol. Today* 16, 364–366.
- Doenhoff, M.J., Cioli, D., Utzinger, J., 2008. Praziquantel: mechanisms of action, resistance and new derivatives for schistosomiasis. *Curr. Opin. Infect. Dis.* 21, 659–667.
- EP 7.0, 2011. In: edition, S. (Ed.), *European Pharmacopoeia*. Directorate for the Quality of Medicines of the Council of Europe, Strasbourg, France.
- Escamilla-Roa, E., Sainz-Díaz, C.I., 2014. Amorphous ammonia-water ice deposited onto silicate grain: effect on growth of mantles ice on interstellar and interplanetary dust. *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118, 3554–3563.
- Espinosa-Lara, J.C., Guzmán-Villanueva, D., Arenas-García, J.I., Herrera-Ruiz, D., Rivera-Islas, J., Román-Bravo, P., Morales-Rojas, H., Höpfl, H., 2013. Cocrystals of active pharmaceutical ingredients-praziquantel in combination with oxalic, malonic, succinic, maleic, fumaric, glutaric, adipic and pimelic acids. *Cryst. Growth Des.* 13, 169–185.
- González-Esquivel, D., Rivera, J., Castro, N., Yopez-Mulia, L., Helgi, J.C., 2005. In vitro characterization of some biopharmaceutical properties of praziquantel. *Int. J. Pharm.* 295, 93–99.

- Greenberg, R.M., 2005. Are Ca²⁺ channels targets of praziquantel action? *Int. J. Parasitol.* 35, 1–9.
- Groll, E., 1984. Praziquantel. *Adv. Pharmacol. Chemother.* 20, 219–238.
- Gross, K., Seybold, P.G., Hadad, C.M., 2002. Comparison of different atomic charge schemes for predicting pK_a variations in substituted anilines and phenols. *Int. J. Quantum Chem.* 90, 445–458.
- Hackey, J.R., Stirewalt, M.A., 1956. Penetration of host skin by cercariae of *S. mansoni*. I. Observed entry into skin of mouse, hamster, rat, monkey and man. *J. Parasitol.* 42, 565–579.
- Hammer, B., Hansen, L.B., Norskov, J.K., 1999. Improved adsorption energetics within density-functional theory using revised Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof functionals. *Phys. Rev. B* 59, 7413.
- Heinz, H., Vaia, R.A., Farmer, L., 2006. Interaction energy and surface reconstruction between sheets of layered silicates. *J. Chem. Phys.* 124, 224713.
- Leopold, G., Ungethüm, W., Groll, E., Diekmann, H.W., Nowak, H., Wegner, D.H.G., 1978. Clinical pharmacology in normal volunteers of praziquantel, a new drug against schistosomes and cestodes. *Eur. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 14, 281–291.
- Lindenberg, M., Kopp, S., Dressman, J.B., 2004. Classification of orally administered drugs on the World Health Organization Model list of essential medicines according to the biopharmaceutics classification system. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 58, 265–278.
- Liu, Y., Wang, X., Wang, J.K., Ching, C.B., 2004. Structural characterization and enantioseparation of the chiral compound praziquantel. *J. Pharm. Sci.* 93, 3039–3046.
- Liu, Y., Wang, X., Wang, J.K., Ching, C.B., 2006. Investigation of the phase diagrams of chiral praziquantel. *Chirality* 18, 259–264.
- Mainardes, R.M., Gremião, M.P.D., Evangelista, R.C., 2006. Thermoanalytical study of praziquantel-loaded PLGA nanoparticles. *Braz. J. Pharm. Sci.* 42, 523–530.
- Martos-Villa, R., Francisco-Márquez, M., Mata, M.P., Sainz-Díaz, C.I., 2013. Crystal structure, stability and spectroscopic properties of methane and CO₂ hydrates. *J. Mol. Graph. Model.* 44, 253–265.
- Meyer, T., Sekljic, H., Fuchs, S., Bothe, H., Schollmeyer, D., Miculka, C., 2009. Taste, a new incentive to switch to (R)-praziquantel in schistosomiasis treatment. *PLoS One* 3, 357.
- Passerini, N., Albertini, B., Perissutti, B., Rodriguez, L., 2006. Evaluation of melt granulation and ultrasonic spray congealing as techniques to enhance the dissolution of praziquantel. *Int. J. Pharm.* 318, 92–102.
- Pax, R., Bennett, J.L., Fetterer, R., 1978. A benzodiazepine derivative and praziquantel: effects on musculature of *Schistosoma mansoni* and *Schistosoma japonicum*. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Arch. Pharmacol.* 304, 309–315.
- Rappe, A.K., Goddard, W.A., 1991. Charge equilibration for molecular dynamics simulations. *J. Phys. Chem.* 95, 3358–3363.
- Rick, S.W., Stuart, S.J., Bader, J.S., Berne, B.J., 1995. Fluctuating charge force fields for aqueous solutions. *J. Mol. Liq.* 65–66, 31–40.
- Rodrigues, S.G., Chaves, I.S., Melo, N.F.S., de Jesus, M.B., Fraceto, L.F., Fernandes, S.A., de Paula, E., de Freitas, M.P., Pinto, L.M.A., 2010. Computational analysis and physico-chemical characterization of an inclusion compound between praziquantel and methyl-β-cyclodextrin for use as an alternative in the treatment of schistosomiasis. *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.* 70, 19–28.
- Sainz-Díaz, C.I., Francisco-Márquez, M., Vivier-Bunge, A., 2011. Adsorption of polyaromatic heterocycles on pyrophyllite surface by different theoretical approaches. *Environ. Chem.* 8, 429–440.
- Schepers, H., Brasseur, R., Goormaghtigh, E., Duquenois, P., Ruyschaert, J.M., 1987. Mode of insertion of praziquantel and derivatives into lipid membranes. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 37, 1615–1623.
- Steinmann, P., Keiser, J., Bos, R., Tanner, M., Utzinger, J., 2006. Schistosomiasis and water resources development: systematic review, meta-analysis, and estimates of people at risk. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* 6, 411–425.
- Sun, H., 1998. COMPASS: an ab initio force-field optimized for condensed-phase applications-overview with details on alkane and benzene compounds. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 102, 7338–7364.
- Toro, R., Kaduk, J., Delgado, M., Díaz de Delgado, G., 2014. Structural characterization of praziquantel: a broad spectrum anthelmintic, in powder diffraction. *Proceedings of the International Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD) Annual Spring Meetings* 29 p. 3.
- Trastullo, R., Dolci, L.S., Passerini, N., Albertini, B., 2015. Development of flexible and dispersible oral formulations containing praziquantel for potential schistosomiasis treatment of pre-school age children. *Int. J. Pharm.* 495, 536–550.
- USP 36-NF31, 2013. *United States Pharmacopoeia 36 and National Formulary 31*. US Pharmacopoeial Convention, Rockville, MD (USA).
- WHO, 2015. *WHO Schistosomiasis*. World Health Organization (<http://www.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs115/en/>).

Further Reading

- Teleman, O., Jonsson, B., Engström, S., 1987. A molecular dynamics simulation of a water model with intramolecular degrees of freedom. *Mol. Phys.* 60, 193–203.